

HyCARE

Hydrogen CARRIER for Renewable Energy Storage

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Data Management Plan

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Executive Summary

According to the Open Research Data Pilot drafted by European Commission, all data generated by H2020 projects have to be open access and reusable: the main aim of ORD pilot in fact, is the improvement and maximization of access to research data, with a special consideration for necessity to balance protection of scientific information, commercialisation and security. A new project participating in ORD Pilot will not share all the available data but would rather follow the principle “As open as possible, As closed as necessary”, enhancing a reliable data tracking and management. The Data Management Plan (DMP) is a document, that will present how data will be used and handled during and after the project: this aspect will be accomplished by a specification of what type of data will become open access, how they will be shared and in what repository, and what methods and standards will be used.

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1. Introduction

The project HyCARE aims at finding a way to store Hydrogen at low temperature and pressure, increasing the technological, economic and safety feasibility and give to market a better possibility of H₂ exploitation. The storage tank, based on technology of Power-to-Solid storage (solid-state hydrogen carrier) and heat storage (it allows the improvement of energy efficiency of overall process), will be installed in site of ENGIE LAB CRIGEN, connected to a 20 kW PEM electrolyser for H₂ injection and to a 10 kW PEM cell for electricity production (demonstration of possible integration with devices for power production).

The main target of project is the demonstration of feasibility of an innovative technology and design (in fact, the storage through MHs has a lower footprint with respect to the liquid or gaseous storage, let's think for instance to the compression cost and technology that would be needed) for higher storage quantity, at low thermodynamic conditions and low environmental impact. These conditions allow a larger market potential with respect to other technologies (CAPEX and OPEX costs are reduced).

The report has the purpose to present the Data Management Plan for HyCARE project and it is part of WP1: Project Management, under responsibility of UNITO. The deliverable is developed by ENVIPARK (UniTo third party) with the support of all the partners.

As first aspect, it is necessary define the meaning of “**Open access**”, that can be defined as the practice of providing on-line free of charge access to scientific information related to project outcomes.

Open access is not a requirement to publish, but it is seen by the European Commission as an approach to facilitate and improve the circulation of information in the European research area and beyond. Open access to some data generated in projects funded by the European commission is the key to lower barriers to accessing publicly-funded research, as well as to demonstrate and share the potential of research activities supported with the help of public funding.

The purpose of this document is to provide the plan for managing the data generated and collected during the project: The Data Management Plan.

Specifically, the DMP describes the data management life cycle for all datasets to be collected, processed and/or generated by a research project. It covers:

- the handling of research data during & after the end of the project
- what data will be collected, processed and/or generated
- which methodology & standards will be applied
- whether data will be shared/made open access and how
- how data will be curated & preserved (including after the end of the project).

The document reports a brief description of the Data Management plan in H2020 program and more in detail the methodology that the consortium used to create the DMP (the policy that the consortium plans to use regarding the data sets collected, processed and/or generated within the project HYCARE).

2. Data Management in H2020 Program

The deliverable is submitted to the Open Research Data Pilot (ORD), a flexible program drafted by European Commission: it concerns the sharing of scientific data and information on specific repositories, in order to enhance the re-use of research data and their exploitation for new studies and future projects. In particular, it is not dealing with scientific peer-reviewed publications (for which open access is an obligation in Horizon 2020¹) but with research data (they could be open or closed), for which the best practise suggested is the sharing with other users, provided the absence of contractual clauses, copyright limits or confidentiality restrictions. In other terms, not only it's necessary to put out scientific publications on specific repositories (download and printing must be made accessible), but it is essential to present also data needed to validate results of scientific publications, so that it's possible to mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate them by any user; concerning other data instead, they can be provided or not (voluntary basis)².

As anticipated, it is not mandatory to have all data produced published, but the principle to be followed is “As open as possible, As closed as necessary”: in this way, the ORD Pilot aims at maximising the access and re-use of research data, without neglecting the aspect of security, Intellectual Property Rights and privacy issues.

The Data Management Plan is the fundamental element necessary for a proper data management: it occupies of all the life cycle of data in a project, making research data FAIR, i.e. Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable³. Therefore, to guarantee the previous characteristics, it must focus on aspects as the way data are collected or generated, on which methodology is applied, whether they are shared or not. Being a document dealing with ‘dynamic’ data, it requires a periodical review to be defined and discussed between the consortium partners.

Open Research Data Pilot project aims at supporting the management of research data, responding at key issues as “what”, “where”, “when”, “how” and “who”⁴

What: The Open Data Pilot covers all research data and associated metadata resulting from EC funded project, if they serve as evidence for publicly available project reports and deliverables or peer reviewed publications.

Where: all public released research data has to be registered and deposited into at least one open data repository.

When: research data related to research publications should made available to the reviewers in the peer review process.

¹ http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/cross-cutting-issues/open-access-data-management/data-management_en.htm

² http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/hi/oa-pilot/h2020-hi-erc-oa-guide_en.pdf

³ http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf

⁴ http://sito.entecra.it/portale/public/documenti/horizon_2020_open_data_pilot.pdf

How: The use of appropriate licenses for Open Data is highly recommended.

Who: Responsibility for the deposit of research data resulting from the project lies with the project coordinator (delegated to project partners where appropriate).

3. Methodology applied for the DMP draft

The Data Management Plan is structured following a precise template, provided by the European Commission: it contains a set of questions to be answered by beneficiaries with an appropriate level of detail (in case of no information available, the phrase “Non-applicable” or acronym N/A will be used).

All the aspects treated in template and concerning the main DMP characteristics are listed and presented hereunder, through the following sections.

The DMP must contain:

- Dataset: identification of data, how it is collected and how it will be used
- Standards and metadata (data relating to the data that describe the properties of the data in a structured way: who created them, who owns them, when they were created ...)
- Data sharing: the data should be made available with open access, otherwise it should be given a reason (opting out).
- Storage and storage methods

3.1. Data summary

In the first section, beneficiaries have to give some specifications; first of all, it is necessary to *investigate the purpose of data* and their *relation with the main objective of project*; moreover, it is necessary to *specify some data formats*, as the *origin of data*, the *utility*, the *expected size* and the possibilities of *re-utilization*.

3.2. FAIR data

F=Findable: Data are findable when they are described by sufficiently rich metadata and registered or indexed in a searchable resource that is known and accessible to potential users. Additionally, a unique and persistent identifier should be assigned such that data can be unequivocally referenced and cited in research communications. The identifier enables persistent linkages to be established between the data, metadata and other related materials in order to assist data discovery and reuse. Related materials may include the code or models necessary to use the data, research literature that provides further insights into the creation and interpretation of the data and other related information.

A=Accessible: data objects can be obtained by humans and machines upon appropriate authorisation and through a well-defined and universally implementable protocol. Anyone with a computer and internet connection should be able to access at least the metadata, but FAIR doesn't mean OPEN without constraint.

I=Interoperable: data and metadata are described in the FAIR principles as those that use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation. The data are described using normative and community recognised specifications, vocabularies and standards that determine the precise meaning of concepts and qualities that the data represent. Technical interoperability means that the data and related information is encoded using a standard that can be read on all applicable systems. In FAIR, legal interoperability falls under the principle that data should be 'Reusable'.

R=Reusable: the FAIR principles reassert the need for rich metadata and documentation that meet relevant community standards and provide information about provenance. Reusability also requires that the data be released with a ‘clear and accessible data usage license’: in other words, the conditions under which the data can be used should be transparent to both humans and machines⁵.

The section below reports:

3.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

All the characteristics concerning how data can be found and collected, by means of specific keywords or numbers, have to be listed in this section, such as their name and format. It is necessary to indicate what metadata will be used or generated to enhance the research phase.

In HyCARE context, in order to design the data set names, we use the following practice done of different parts separated with an underscore: *HyCARE_ WP_{no}_ YYYYMMDD_ Partner name_ On_ dataset name*

- A. First the project name: *HyCARE*
- B. the work package number, *WP_{no}*
- C. the date using *YYYYMMDD* (format that insures direct correspondence between chronological and alphabetical orders),
- D. the *Partner name*, who produced the data,
- E. the serial number of the dataset within the work package, serial numbering will be performed by 2 digits to make consistent alphabetical and chronological filing, *On*
- F. *dataset name*, all separated with underscore (*HYCARE_Data_WPno_YYYYMMDD_ data producer ID _<serial number of dataset (2 digits)>_<dataset title>*).

An example can be the following:

HYCARE_WP7_20190910_ENGIE_01_ Test of integrating system.

In reality, this precise naming should be applied to the general dataset: each separate file will follow the conventional name proposed by partner having created it.

3.2.2 Making data accessible

In the following section, it is fundamental to specify which data will be made available and which not, and why.

It is possible in fact that some beneficiaries should choose to keep their data closed, provided suitable justifications: the partner involved has to describe if there are legal, contractual or ethical impediments.

Moreover, it must be pointed out where the data/metadata will be available (in what repository, whether the use of specific software or tools is necessary etc.) and how (for instance, in which way the access should be provided in case of restrictions, or in which way the identity of a person searching will be ascertained).

There are some available specific repositories such as: OpenAIRE⁶, The Registry of Research Data Repositories⁷, Zenodo⁸, arXiv⁹.

3.2.3 Making data interoperable

The data providers must specify what vocabularies and methodology have to be used to guarantee a suitable exchange and re-use among institutions, researchers and companies.

⁵ Turning FAIR into reality 2018, https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/turning_fair_into_reality_1.pdf

⁶ <https://www.openaire.eu/>

⁷ <http://www.re3data.org/>

⁸ <https://zenodo.org/>

⁹ <https://arxiv.org/>

3.2.4 Increase data re-use through clarifying licenses

Some specifications must be postulated regarding the re-utilisation of data, such as the type of licenses exploited, the period in which data will be available (so, for how much time data can be found and re-used in other researches), whether it is forecast the use by third parties before the end of project and if such data have limitations or not.

3.2.5 Allocation of resources

All costs related to FAIR data management must be assessed and it must be specified in which way they will be covered. All the other expenses must be discussed with the designated project coordinator.

Along the HyCARE project the DMP is managed by UNITO as coordinator of the project and of WP1. The costs and so the allocated resources are part of the allocated costs in the project.

The partners will decide and describe the procedures that will be used in order to ensure long-term preservation of the data sets. This field will provide information regarding the duration of the data preservation, the approximate end volume, the associated costs and the plans of the consortium to cover the costs.

3.2.6 Data security

A special attention will be given to security of sensitive data (not only concerning data recovery, but also their transfer and storage), which necessitate for protection through specific technologies and expedients.

3.2.7 Ethical aspects

Any ethical issue involved in project must be discussed in this section and if there are any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing they can be discussed in this context.

3.2.8 Other issues

Any national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedure, if used, must be highlighted here.

4. Methodology applied for the DMP HYCARE

4.1 Different types of data sets

The first aspect the HyCARE consortium has to evaluate, is the identification of different datasets, at this early stage of the project. Table 1 gives an overview of all the data that are expected to be collected or generated by the HyCARE project.

The project presents different types divided also with the different activities in the WPs: experimental data, characterization data, publications data, modelling data, documents data.

WPs	Data type (experimental/characterization/publications/documents)	Data description	Partner responsible	Data standard (.csv/.png/.pdf/.xls/.docx/.txt...)	Open/restricted	Sharing	Preservation duration
2. Carrier tailoring and testing	Experimental/characterization/documents	T2.1: experiments in order to optimize the alloy composition; characterizations (Xrays, gravimetry, PCT); T2.2: activation process experiment; T2.3: impurity and cyclability experiments	CNRS, UNITO, IFE	.xls, png and jpg; docx; pdf.	Restricted; to evaluate during the first meeting if specific data can be open. However, some data will be present in scientific publications	Data shared between partners using a specific platform (Google Drive)	
3. Carrier production and processing	Experimental/documents/characterization	T3.1: powder creation via specific processes; T3.2: lab characterization of the produced powder	GKN SM, UNITO, HZG, CNRS, IFE	.xls, png and jpg; docx; pdf.	Some data will be open; the lab tests data are restricted	Data shared between partners using a specific platform (Google Drive)	
4. Heat management	Experimental/characterization/documents	T4.1: Heat recovery system design and characterization; T4.2: FEM analysis and validation; T4.3: Detailed drawings and heat storage tank building of the system	TECNODELTA, FBK	.xls, png and jpg; docx; pdf.; .solidworks; .dwg; Inventors ipt, iam and idw, stp	Some data will be open; detailed drawing data are restricted	Data shared between partners using a specific platform (Google Drive)	
5. Tank project and building	Experimental/characterization/documents/modelling	T5.1: project of the tank; T5.2: FEM analysis, modelling and lab validation; T5.3: tank construction and test	TECNODELTA, UNITO, ENGIE, Stühff GmbH	.xls, png and jpg; docx; pdf.; .solidworks; .dwg; Inventors ipt, iam and idw, stp	Some data will be open; detailed drawing data are restricted	Data shared between partners using a specific platform (Google Drive)	

WPs	Data type (experimental/characterization/publications/documents)	Data description	Partner responsible	Data standard (.csv/.png/.pdf/.xls/.docx/.txt...)	Open/restricted	Sharing	Preservation duration
6. System integration	Experimental/modelling	T6.1: electric and fluid dynamic scheme of ENGI site; T6.2: data from modelling of	ENGIE, UNITO, GKN, TD, STH, FBK, HZ	.solidworks;.cad; .docx; .xls; Inventors ipt, iam and idw, stp	Market restricted	Data shared between partners using a specific platform (Google Drive)	
7. System commissioning and validation	Experimental/documents	T7.1: P&I of integrated systems and safety analysis; T7.2: control strategy on PLC platform; T7.3: commissioning manual; T7.4: experimental tests	ENGIE	.jpeg; .pdf; .txt; .vi; .docx	Market restricted	Data shared between partners using a specific platform (Google Drive)	
8. Evaluation, exploitation, dissemination and communication	Documents and publications	T8.1: Techno-economical evaluation document; T8.2: LCA analysis document and data calculated; T8.3: communication activities via newsletter, website, leaflet; dissemination activities via papers, conferences, posters, presentations at thematic workshops and scientific conferences; T8.4: exploitation and market deployment plan document	UNITO, FBK	.docx, .pdf, .pptx,	Some data and documents Open	Websserver; EU's public repositories, OpenAIRE and Zenodo	

The sections below follow the scheme of the H2020 template of Data management plan³, with more details for each WPs.

4.2 WP 2: Carrier tailoring and testing

DMP component	Issues addressed_WP2
1. Data summary	<p><i>Purpose of the data:</i> Characterization of the composition of alloy, focusing on composition tailoring, determination of activation conditions and cyclability of H₂ sorption reaction. Experiment in order to optimize the alloy composition.</p> <p><i>Data types and format:</i> .xls, png and jpg; docx; pdf.</p> <p><i>Re-use of existing data and if yes, how?</i> Yes, some experimental data from partners are the starting point for these studies.</p> <p><i>Origin of data:</i> Determination from suitable models (ex. to establish the kinetics of hydrogen sorption reaction) and from experimental analysis made on purpose by partners (ex. X-ray diffraction, thermal treatments, hydrogen cycling etc.).</p> <p><i>Expected size of data:</i> Roughly several Gb</p> <p><i>To whom will it be useful?</i> Industrial private sector, university researchers, scientific community.</p>
2. FAIR Data	
2.1 Making data findable	<p><i>Description of the data/naming/keywords:</i> The naming will be the following: <i>WP_{no}_YYYYMMDD_Partner name_On_dataset name_type</i> (type is the kind of experimental analysis, ex <i>WP2_20190505_unito_01_chatacterization_xray.jpg</i>)</p>
2.2 Making data accessible	<p><i>Which data and how will be made openly available?</i> At this stage the data present in WP2 are restricted: tests and characterizations. In case of Confidential data (shared with Consortium members, including the Commission Services), it will be necessary to insert data and information exclusively on the portal shared with Consortium members (forbidden to other users). Data will be made first published in scientific publications and later it will be possible made public graphical outputs.</p> <p><i>What method or software tools are needed to access the data? Is documentation about the software needed to</i></p>

	<p><i>access the data included? Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?</i> N/A</p> <p><i>Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited?</i> Confidential data will be exclusively published on a private portal, to be only shared with the other partners.</p> <p><i>Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository?</i> N/A if we have explicated that data are restricted</p> <p><i>If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?</i> N/A if we have explicated that data are restricted</p> <p><i>Is there a need for access (i.e. machine readable license)?</i> N/A data available only in a portal accessible to all the partners</p>
<p>2.3 Making data interoperable</p>	<p><i>What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?</i> Most of data published are considered interoperable by nature, i.e. they can be searched and found by using normal keywords, maybe associated each other, in order to focus on a precise item.</p> <p><i>Will you be using standard vocabularies for all data types present in your dataset, to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability?</i> Yes, if possible. It may happen in fact that one single search is helpful for several information provided, not only for a single one.</p> <p><i>In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mapping to more commonly used ontologies?</i> In case of specific vocabulary used, a proper legend will be provided, to give a clear and specific explanation of the possible searching mode.</p>
<p>2.4. Increase data re-use</p>	<p><i>How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?</i> N/A</p> <p><i>When will the data be made available for re-use? If an embargo is sought to give time to publish or seek patents, specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.</i> N/A</p>

	<p><i>Are the data produced and/o used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why.</i> N/A</p> <p><i>How long is intended that the data remains re-usable?</i> N/A</p> <p><i>Are data quality assurance processes described?</i></p>
3. Allocation of resources	<p><i>What are the costs for making data FAIR? How will these be covered? Who will be responsible for data management?</i> The costs are covered by the project.</p>
4. Data security	<p><i>What provisions are in place for data security?</i> The partners will charge all the data restricted on a platform (Google drive proposed)</p> <p><i>Is the data safety stored for long term preservation and curation?</i> To be defined</p>
5. Ethical aspects	N/A
6. Other	N/A

4.2 WP 3: Carrier production and processing

DMP component	Issues addressed_WP3
1. Data summary	<p><i>Purpose of the data:</i> Definition of production methods for powders and pellets, by testing phases as vacuum melting, crushing, sieving. It is followed by manufacturing and production, with consequent quality and mechanical controls.</p> <p><i>Data types and format:</i> .xls, png and jpg; docx; pdf.</p> <p><i>Re-use of existing data and if yes, how?</i> Yes, some experimental data from partners are the starting point for these studies.</p> <p><i>Origin of data:</i> Mainly from experimental field (vacuum testing, crushing, sieving, cyclability and activation parameters, neutron experiments).</p> <p><i>Expected size of data:</i> Roughly several Gb</p>

	<p><i>To whom will it be useful?</i> Industrial private sector, university researchers, scientific community.</p>
<p>2. FAIR Data</p>	
<p>2.1 Making data findable</p>	<p><i>Description of the data/naming/keywords:</i> The naming will be the following: <i>WP_{no}_YYYYMMDD_Partner name_On_dataset name_type</i> (type is the kind of experimental analysis, ex <i>WP3_20190505_CNRS_01_chatacterization_SEM.jpg</i>)</p>
<p>2.2 Making data accessible</p>	<p><i>Which data and how will be made openly available?</i> At this stage the data present in WP3 are restricted: tests and characterizations. In case of Confidential data (shared with Consortium members, including the Commission Services), it will be necessary to insert data and information exclusively on the portal shared with Consortium members (forbidden to other users). Some data will be open; the lab tests data are restricted.</p> <p><i>What method or software tools are needed to access the data? Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included?Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?</i> N/A</p> <p><i>Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited?</i> Confidential data instead will be exclusively published on a private portal, to be only shared with the other partners.</p> <p><i>Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository?</i> <i>If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?</i> N/A if we have explicated that data are restricted</p> <p><i>Is there a need for access (i.e. machine readable license)?</i> <i>How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?</i> N/A data available only in a portal accessible to all the partners via user and password</p>
<p>2.3 Making data interoperable</p>	<p><i>What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?</i> Most of data published are considered interoperable by nature, i.e. they can be searched and found by using normal</p>

	<p>keywords, maybe associated each other, in order to focus on a precise item.</p> <p><i>Will you be using standard vocabularies for all data types present in your dataset, to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability?</i></p> <p>Yes, if possible. It may happen in fact that one single search is helpful for several information provided, not only for a single one.</p> <p><i>In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mapping to more commonly used ontologies?</i></p> <p>In case of specific vocabulary used, a proper legend will be provided, to give a clear and specific explanation of the possible searching mode.</p>
<p>2.4. Increase data re-use</p>	<p><i>How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?</i></p> <p>N/A</p> <p><i>When will the data be made available for re-use? If an embargo is sought to give time to publish or seek patents, specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.</i></p> <p>N/A</p> <p><i>Are the data produced and/o used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why.</i></p> <p>N/A</p> <p><i>How long is intended that the data remains re-usable?</i></p> <p>N/A</p> <p><i>Are data quality assurance processes described?</i></p>
<p>3. Allocation of resources</p>	<p><i>What are the costs for making data FAIR?</i></p> <p><i>How will these be covered?</i></p> <p><i>Who will be responsible for data management?</i></p> <p>The costs are covered by the project.</p>
<p>4. Data security</p>	<p><i>What provisions are in place for data security?</i></p> <p>The partners will charge all the data restricted on a platform (Google drive proposed)</p> <p><i>Is the data safety stored for long term preservation and curation?</i> To be defined</p>
<p>5. Ethical aspects</p>	<p>N/A</p>
<p>6. Other</p>	<p>N/A</p>

4.3 WP 4: Heat management

DMP component	Issues addressed_WP4
<p>1. Data summary</p>	<p>Purpose of the data: Heat recovery system selection, characterization and design: different studies are made on PCM materials, to better understand behaviour during the phase change. Hence, heat storage tank modelling and validation (analysis of different shapes, FEM simulations and risk analysis) and finally model building.</p> <p>Data types and format: .xls, png and jpg; docx; pdf, solidworks , dwg. Inventors ipt, iam and idw, stp.</p> <p>Re-use of existing data and if yes, how? Yes, some experimental data from partners are the starting point for these studies. In this case, an example could be the fact that activity is linked to WP2 for the definition of Transition Temperature, or with WP5 for the integration of heat storage system and hydrogen storage tank.</p> <p>Origin of data: Mainly from experimental field (vacuum testing, crushing, sieving, cyclability and activation parameters, neutron experiments). Data are determined by experiments (working cycles, safety tests) and models (FEM analysis of thermal exchanges inside the PCM).</p> <p>Expected size of data: Roughly several Gb</p> <p>To whom might it be useful? Industrial private sector, university researchers, scientific community.</p>
<p>2. FAIR Data</p>	
<p>2.1 Making data findable</p>	<p>Description of the data/naming/keywords: The naming will be the following: <i>WP_{no}_YYYYMMDD_Partner name_0n_dataset name_type</i> (type is the kind of experimental analysis, ex <i>WP4_20190505_Tecnodelta_01_chatacterization_FEM.jpg</i>)</p>
<p>2.2 Making data accessible</p>	<p>Which data and how will be made openly available? At this stage the data present in WP4 are restricted: tests and characterizations. In case of Confidential data (shared with Consortium members, including the Commission Services), it will be necessary to insert data and information exclusively on the</p>

	<p>portal shared with Consortium members (forbidden to other users). Some data will be open; detailed drawing data are restricted.</p> <p><i>What method or software tools are needed to access the data? Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included? Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?</i> N/A</p> <p><i>Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited?</i> Confidential data instead will be exclusively published on a private portal, to be only shared with the other partners.</p> <p><i>Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository?</i> <i>If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?</i> N/A if we have explicated that data are restricted</p> <p><i>Is there a need for access (i.e. machine readable license)?</i> <i>How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?</i> N/A data available only in a portal accessible to all the partners via user and password</p>
<p>2.3 Making data interoperable</p>	<p><i>What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?</i> Most of data published are considered interoperable by nature, i.e. they can be searched and found by using normal keywords, maybe associated each other, in order to focus on a precise item.</p> <p><i>Will you be using standard vocabularies for all data types present in your dataset, to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability?</i> Yes, if possible. It may happen in fact that one single search is helpful for several information provided, not only for a single one.</p> <p><i>In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mapping to more commonly used ontologies?</i> In case of specific vocabulary used, a proper legend will be provided, to give a clear and specific explanation of the possible searching mode.</p>
<p>2.4. Increase data re-use</p>	<p><i>How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?</i> N/A</p> <p><i>When will the data be made available for re-use? If an embargo is sought to give time to publish or seek patents,</i></p>

	<p><i>specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.</i></p> <p>N/A</p> <p><i>Are the data produced and/o used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why.</i></p> <p>N/A</p> <p><i>How long is intended that the data remains re-usable?</i></p> <p>N/A</p> <p><i>Are data quality assurance processes described?</i></p>
3. Allocation of resources	<p><i>What are the costs for making data FAIR?</i></p> <p><i>How will these be covered?</i></p> <p><i>Who will be responsible for data management?</i></p> <p>The costs are covered by the project.</p>
4. Data security	<p><i>What provisions are in place for data security?</i></p> <p>The partners will charge all the data restricted on a platform (Google drive proposed)</p> <p><i>Is the data safety stored for long term preservation and curation?</i> To be defined</p>
5. Ethical aspects	N/A
6. Other	N/A

4.4 WP 5: Tank project and building

DMP component	Issues addressed_WP5
1. Data summary	<p><i>Purpose of the data:</i></p> <p>Realization of hydrogen tank, starting from the project (based on previous analysis made by partners in WP2 and WP3), passing to the tank modelling and validation (use of FEM analysis and software as Comsol Multiphysics) and concluding with building and preliminary testing.</p> <p><i>Data types and format:</i> .xls, png and jpg; docx; pdf. Inventors ipt, iam and idw, stp</p> <p><i>Re-use of existing data and if yes, how?</i></p> <p>Yes, some experimental data from partners are the starting point for these studies. Moreover, investigation is based on</p>

	<p>existing European Standards, as the Pressure Equipment Device PED 2014/68/EU and the EN 13 445.</p> <p>Origin of data: Data are determined by application of existing regulations, but also by experimental investigation (tank testing and filling) and models (FEM analysis of the tank).</p> <p>Expected size of data: Roughly several Gb</p> <p>To whom might it be useful? Industrial private sector, university researchers, scientific community.</p>
<p>2. FAIR Data</p>	
<p>2.1 Making data findable</p>	<p>Description of the data: The naming will be the following: <i>WP_{no}_YYYYMMDD_Partner name_On_dataset name_type</i> (type is the kind of experimental analysis, ex <i>WP5_20190505_Tecnodelta_01_P&I.jpg</i>)</p>
<p>2.2 Making data accessible</p>	<p>Which data and how will be made openly available? At this stage the data present in W5 are restricted: tests and characterizations. In case of Confidential data (shared with Consortium members, including the Commission Services), it will be necessary to insert data and information exclusively on the portal shared with Consortium members (forbidden to other users). Some data will be open; detailed drawing data are restricted</p> <p>What method or software tools are needed to access the data? Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included? Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)? N/A</p> <p>Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited? Confidential data instead will be exclusively published on a private portal, to be only shared with the other partners.</p> <p>Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository?</p> <p>If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided? N/A if we have explicated that data are restricted</p> <p>Is there a need for access (i.e. machine readable license)?</p> <p>How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained? N/A data available only in a portal accessible to all the partners via user and password</p>

<p>2.3 Making data interoperable</p>	<p><i>What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?</i></p> <p>Most of data published are considered interoperable by nature, i.e. they can be searched and found by using normal keywords, maybe associated each other, in order to focus on a precise item.</p> <p><i>Will you be using standard vocabularies for all data types present in your dataset, to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability?</i></p> <p>Yes, if possible. It may happen in fact that one single search is helpful for several information provided, not only for a single one.</p> <p><i>In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mapping to more commonly used ontologies?</i></p> <p>In case of specific vocabulary used, a proper legend will be provided, to give a clear and specific explanation of the possible searching mode.</p>
<p>2.4. Increase data re-use</p>	<p><i>How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?</i></p> <p>N/A</p> <p><i>When will the data be made available for re-use? If an embargo is sought to give time to publish or seek patents, specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.</i></p> <p>N/A</p> <p><i>Are the data produced and/o used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why.</i></p> <p>N/A</p> <p><i>How long is intended that the data remains re-usable?</i></p> <p>N/A</p> <p><i>Are data quality assurance processes described?</i></p>
<p>3. Allocation of resources</p>	<p><i>What are the costs for making data FAIR?</i></p> <p><i>How will these be covered?</i></p> <p><i>Who will be responsible for data management?</i></p> <p>The costs are covered by the project.</p>
<p>4. Data security</p>	<p><i>What provisions are in place for data security?</i></p> <p>The partners will charge all the data restricted on a platform (Google drive proposed)</p> <p><i>Is the data safety stored for long term preservation and curation?</i> To be defined</p>

5. Ethical aspects	N/A
6. Other	N/A

4.5 WP 6: System integration

DMP component	Issues addressed_WP6
1. Data summary	<p><i>Purpose of the data:</i> Setup a model of integrated hydrogen-heat-storage system, under the chemical, physical and thermal point of view. It is combined with an optimization of mass and energy flows in the whole system (electrolyser, hydrogen and heat storage, fuel cell).</p> <p><i>Data type and format:</i> .xls/xlsx, png and jpg; doc/docx; pdf. Inventors ipt, iam and idw, stp</p> <p><i>Re-use of existing data and if yes, how?</i> Yes, some experimental data from partners are the starting point for these studies. For instance, the use of a suitable system for contaminants removal, based on different existing technologies (and so, existing data); moreover, this Work Package is operating contemporarily and in close connection with WP4 and WP5</p> <p><i>Origin of data:</i> The originated data derive mostly from experiments (tests to simulate real working conditions) and application of theoretical and software modelling.</p> <p><i>Expected size of data:</i> Roughly several Gb</p> <p><i>To whom might it be useful?</i> Industrial private sector, university researchers, scientific community.</p>
2. FAIR Data	
2.1 Making data findable	<p><i>Description of the data:</i> The naming will be the following: $WP_{no_}YYYYMMDD_Partner\ name_On_dataset\ name_type$ (type is the kind of experimental analysis, ex $WP6_20190505_ENGIE_01_design.jpg$)</p>

2.2 Making data accessible

Which data and how will be made openly available?

At this stage the data present in WP6 are restricted. In case of Confidential data (shared with Consortium members, including the Commission Services), it will be necessary to insert data and information exclusively on the portal shared with Consortium members (forbidden to other users).

What method or software tools are needed to access the data? Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included? Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)? N/A

Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited?

Confidential data instead will be exclusively published on a private portal, to be only shared with the other partners.

Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository?

If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?

N/A if we have explicated that data are restricted

Is there a need for access (i.e. machine-readable license)?

How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?

N/A data available only in a portal accessible to all the partners via user and password

2.3 Making data interoperable

What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?

Most of data published are considered interoperable by nature, i.e. they can be searched and found by using normal keywords, maybe associated each other, in order to focus on a precise item.

Will you be using standard vocabularies for all data types present in your dataset, to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability?

Yes, if possible. It may happen, in fact, that one single search is helpful for several information provided, not just for a single one.

In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

In case of specific vocabulary used, a proper legend will be provided, to give a clear and specific explanation of the possible searching mode.

<p>2.4. Increase data re-use</p>	<p><i>How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?</i> N/A</p> <p><i>When will the data be made available for re-use? If an embargo is sought to give time to publish or seek patents, specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.</i> N/A</p> <p><i>Are the data produced and/o used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why.</i> N/A</p> <p><i>How long is intended that the data remains re-usable?</i> N/A</p> <p><i>Are data quality assurance processes described?</i></p>
<p>3. Allocation of resources</p>	<p><i>What are the costs for making data FAIR?</i> It is hard to estimate at this stage of development.</p> <p><i>How will these be covered?</i> The costs shall be covered by the project budget.</p> <p><i>Who will be responsible for data management?</i> The data management responsibility is on the project coordinator and on the partner, who generated the data.</p>
<p>4. Data security</p>	<p><i>What provisions are in place for data security?</i> The partners will charge all the data restricted on a platform (Google drive proposed)</p> <p><i>Is the data safety stored for long term preservation and curation?</i> To be defined</p>
<p>5. Ethical aspects</p>	<p>N/A</p>
<p>6. Other</p>	<p>N/A</p>

4.6 WP 7: System commissioning and validation

<p>DMP component</p>	<p>Issues addressed_WP7</p>
<p>1. Data summary</p>	<p><i>Purpose of the data:</i> Implementation of the whole system (made by heat and H2 storage, coupled with a PEM electrolyser and a PEM fuel cell) and testing within some relevant working conditions.</p> <p><i>Data type and format:</i> .xls, png and jpg; docx; pdf.</p> <p><i>Re-use of existing data and if yes, how?</i></p>

	<p>WP7 is receiving in fact the results obtained by partners of WP4 and WP5 (realization of heat and hydrogen storage), together with data of WP6 (integration of the whole system)</p> <p>Origin of data: The originated data derive mostly from experiments (check of status of electrical, mechanical, instrument installation during last phase of pre-commissioning, and running) and application of analysis as ATEX, HAZOP, danger analysis</p> <p>Expected size of data: Roughly several Gb</p> <p>To whom might it be useful? Industrial private sector, university researchers, scientific community.</p>
<p>2. FAIR Data</p>	
<p>2.1 Making data findable</p>	<p>Description of the data: The naming will be the following: <i>WP_{no}_YYYYMMDD_Partner name_On_dataset name_type</i> (type is the kind of experimental analysis, ex <i>WP7_20190505_ENGIE_01_validation.excel</i>)</p>
<p>2.2 Making data accessible</p>	<p>Which data and how will be made openly available? At this stage the data present in WP7 are restricted. In case of Confidential data (shared with Consortium members, including the Commission Services), it will be necessary to insert data and information exclusively on the portal shared with Consortium members (forbidden to other users).</p> <p>What method or software tools are needed to access the data? Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included? Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)? N/A</p> <p>Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited? Confidential data instead will be exclusively published on a private portal, to be only shared with the other partners.</p> <p>Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository?</p> <p>If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided? N/A if we have explicated that data are restricted</p> <p>Is there a need for access (i.e. machine readable license)?</p> <p>How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?</p>

	<p>N/A data available only in a portal accessible to all the partners via user and password</p>
<p>2.3 Making data interoperable</p>	<p><i>What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?</i></p> <p>Most of data published are considered interoperable by nature, i.e. they can be searched and found by using normal keywords, maybe associated each other, in order to focus on a precise item.</p> <p><i>Will you be using standard vocabularies for all data types present in your dataset, to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability?</i></p> <p>Yes, if possible. It may happen in fact that one single search is helpful for several information provided, not only for a single one.</p> <p><i>In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mapping to more commonly used ontologies?</i></p> <p>In case of specific vocabulary used, a proper legend will be provided, to give a clear and specific explanation of the possible searching mode.</p>
<p>2.4. Increase data re-use</p>	<p><i>How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?</i></p> <p>N/A</p> <p><i>When will the data be made available for re-use? If an embargo is sought to give time to publish or seek patents, specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.</i></p> <p>N/A</p> <p><i>Are the data produced and/o used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why.</i></p> <p>N/A</p> <p><i>How long is intended that the data remains re-usable?</i></p> <p>N/A</p> <p><i>Are data quality assurance processes described?</i></p>
<p>3. Allocation of resources</p>	<p><i>What are the costs for making data FAIR?</i></p> <p><i>How will these be covered?</i></p> <p><i>Who will be responsible for data management?</i></p> <p>The costs are covered by the project.</p>
<p>4. Data security</p>	<p><i>What provisions are in place for data security?</i></p> <p>The partners will charge all the data restricted on a platform</p>

	(Google drive proposed) <i>Is the data safety stored for long term preservation and curation?</i> To be defined
5. Ethical aspects	N/A
6. Other	N/A

4.7 WP 8: Evaluation, exploitation, dissemination and communication

DMP component	Issues addressed_WP8
1. Data summary	<p>Purpose of the data: Final evaluation of the project, including a techno-economical evaluation and LCA analysis. Suitable Dissemination and Communication plan and Exploitation plan will be designed and implemented, in order to have a successful and effective exploitation of obtained results.</p> <p>Data type and format: xlsx; png and jpg; docx; pdf</p> <p>Re-use of existing data and if yes, how? Yes, some data from partners are the starting point for these studies.</p> <p>Origin of data: Data derive mainly by the other WPs: input for LCA analysis and economical evaluation. Scientific papers from the partners. Exploitable results from the partners, managed considering IPRs.</p> <p>Expected size of data: From Mb to Gb</p> <p>To whom might it be useful? Industrial private sector, university researchers, scientific community, policy makers.</p>
2. FAIR Data	
2.1 Making data findable	<p>Description of the data: The naming will be the following: <i>WP_{no}_YYYYMMDD_Partner name_0n_dataset name</i> (ex WP8_20190505_unito_01_publication)</p>

<p>2.2 Making data accessible</p>	<p><i>Which data and how will be made openly available?</i> Data available using the project website, via each partner dissemination activities, using scientific publications (OpenAccess).</p> <p><i>Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited?</i> Open data will be made available on European portal ZeNODO. Confidential data instead will be exclusively published on a private portal, to be only shared with the other partners.</p> <p><i>Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository?</i> Homepage of the project will be managed by FBK http://www.hycare-project.eu/. Confidential data will be deposited in private portal (Google Drive) accessible to the partners.</p> <p><i>If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?</i> N/A</p> <p><i>Is there a need for access (i.e. machine-readable license)?</i> <i>How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?</i> N/A</p>
<p>2.3 Making data interoperable</p>	<p><i>What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?</i> Most of data published are considered interoperable by nature, i.e. they can be searched and found by using normal keywords, maybe associated each other, in order to focus on a precise item.</p> <p><i>Will you be using standard vocabularies for all data types present in your dataset, to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability?</i> Yes, if possible. It may happen in fact that one single search is helpful for several information provided, not only for a single one.</p> <p><i>In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mapping to more commonly used ontologies?</i> In case of specific vocabulary used, a proper legend will be provided, to give a clear and specific explanation of the possible searching mode.</p>
<p>2.4. Increase data re-use</p>	<p><i>How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?</i></p>

	<p>N/A</p> <p><i>When will the data be made available for re-use? If an embargo is sought to give time to publish or seek patents, specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible?</i></p> <p>N/A</p> <p><i>Are the data produced and/o used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why.</i></p> <p>N/A</p> <p><i>How long is intended that the data remains re-usable?</i></p> <p>N/A</p>
<p>3. Allocation of resources</p>	<p><i>What are the costs for making data FAIR? How will these be covered?</i></p> <p>Covered by the project</p> <p><i>Who will be responsible for data management?</i></p> <p>The project coordinator (UniTo)</p>
<p>4. Data security</p>	<p><i>What provisions are in place for data security?</i></p> <p>The partners will charge the data restricted on a platform (Google Drive proposed)</p> <p><i>Is the data safety stored for long term preservation and curation?</i></p> <p>It is supposed that Data Safety and Security is provided for all the time data are deposited in repository.</p>
<p>5. Ethical aspects</p>	<p>N/A</p>
<p>6. Other</p>	<p>N/A</p>

5. Conclusions

The present document has intended to outline a preliminary strategy for the management of data generated throughout HyCARE project. Considering that this deliverable is due at month six, few datasets have been generated yet, so it is possible that in the future some aspects outlined in the present document will need to be refined or adjusted.

The consortium during the M6 meeting has decided to store all data collected restricted during the project in an online data repository (Google drive) and Zenodo as suitable “Open Access” repository.